

Subnetworks: A Novel Architectural Paradigm for 6G

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Abstract—The anticipated collaborative use cases in 6G come with extreme requirements in latency and throughput. At the same time, network densification is expected to continue, thus making those more stringent requirements tougher to satisfy. To accommodate this, we propose a novel architecture for subnetworks (SNs), a paradigm shift compared to the more centralized cellular systems today. These SNs are formed among user equipments (UEs) with aid of a new UE role, the Management Node (MgtN), which is also introduced. As a result, a novel SN architecture is presented, where the user and control planes of the UEs and the MgtN are described. With SNs, the functionalities are distributed among the different nodes in the SN. Additionally, new processes are defined to maintain network connectivity within the SN in the form of the SN tunneling (SN-TP) and routing (SN-RP) protocols. The new architecture is designed with the aim of enabling a higher degree of independence of the SN in a network of networks.

Index Terms—subnetworks, MgtN, 6G, SN-TP, SN-RP

I. INTRODUCTION

The vision for 6G [1] involves ubiquitous digitalization and connectivity. Therefore, several new *Use Cases* (UC) have been discussed in the standardization bodies [2]. One of the most prominent UCs is the collaborative UC [3], where several users interact with each other, while at the same time requiring connection with the overlay network. Naturally, this UC involves extreme latency, throughput, computation and power requirements for both local and external traffic. The anticipated UCs would involve many mobile devices that are collaborating in highly dynamic scenarios with frequent changes in Network (NW) topology and QoS requirements. Additionally, NW densification is expected to continue, imposing increased cost on the NW due to the associated control overhead. Optimizing those control procedures in the NW often requires sharing of *User Equipment* (UE) sensitive information with the NW, thus leading to privacy and security concerns. All those aspects mandate a paradigm shift from the traditional network-centric architecture towards a more decentralized architecture with more UE autonomy and independence from the NW. Additionally, under the current cellular framework all nodes are required to be fully 3GPP-compliant [2]. As a consequence, the UE complexity is significantly increased, thus driving the development cost up. As a remedy, reduced-complexity UE types could be deployed using a collaborative entity to offload some of the NW and the UE functionalities. Therefore, the novel architecture should ensure scalability, collaboration as well as adaptations to a dynamic environment, while guaranteeing user privacy. For this reason, the concept of network-of-networks, where *User Equipment* (UEs) are organized in

hierarchical subnetworks (SNs), has been advocated [4] in order to meet those extreme requirements, albeit without a concrete architectural framework.

Regarding the current 3GPP architectural framework, *Integrated Access and Backhaul* (IAB) [5], *Sidelink* (SL) and SL relay [6] may not be viable options to realize SN operations. Although mobility of the last IAB node in an IAB tree is currently supported [7], IAB is not meant for flexible and dynamic UC-driven formation of SNs of UEs, as IAB nodes are BSs under tight NW control and are part of the operator-owned RAN. This yields significant delay overheads in dynamic collaborative scenarios, as potential adaptations in the local network would have to stem from the donor IAB. In fact, this also yields a privacy concern, since devices engaging in local communication have to share more information with the NW owned RAN nodes. As for 3GPP SL and SL relay [6], the former only focuses on UE-to-UE communication in a *device-to-device* (D2D) manner avoiding the need for data to go through the BS, while the latter extends the cellular coverage via relaying data through an SL relay UE towards a BS. Despite SL Mode 2 [6] relying on a higher degree of UE autonomy, the D2D links in this mode are established in a completely ad-hoc manner, thus involving delay overheads owing to random channel access. In SL relay, the NW control even spans across the relay UE that is controlled via the Sidelink Relay Adaptation Protocol [8] and the communication among different UEs is defined as individual peer-to-peer links via the PC5 interface rather than a more independent SN formed among UEs. The PC5 interface is under tight NW control, resulting in delays when adapting to changes in the dynamic environment. Similar to the IAB, the tight NW control of SL communication becomes a privacy concern, since it requires the UEs to share information regarding SN-internal communication with the NW, which could otherwise be handled within the SN. Additionally, SL relay focuses solely on *User Plane* (UP) functionality and the relaying of user data, which serves only specific use cases (e.g., out-of-coverage UEs). Apart from the aforementioned 3GPP technologies, traditional WiFi hotspot or *tethering* [9] offers a more user-centric solution, yet it provides no integration to the overlay NW, and thus offers no end-to-end QoS guarantees.

Therefore, no existing framework capitalizes on offloading of certain *Control Plane* (CP) functionalities among UEs. Explicitly, CP functionality offloading, such as local scheduling coordination, is crucial for guaranteeing the aforementioned extreme requirements, as it would enable neighboring nodes'

collaboration, leading to potential gains in nodes' capabilities. In fact, in the collaborative UCs there may exist several highly-capable nodes that could assist lower capability nodes. To the authors' knowledge there has been no proposed framework for control plane offloading in the literature. Additionally, this functional offloading requires trust and security to be established among the UEs of the SN. In the collaborative 6G UCs [2], this can be facilitated by the locality of the SN nodes. For instance, an SN could be formed by devices of a single user or of a family or of a group of friends. This in turn improves user privacy, as sensitive UE information is only shared within the trusted SN and not with the overlay NW. In this paper, we propose a novel user-centric architecture for SNs, where CP and UP functionality can be distributed among the SN nodes. More specifically, our contributions are summarized as follows:

- We propose the new UE role of the Management Node (MgtN), which manages the SN.
- Based on this new UE role, we distribute the network functionality within the SN and propose the flexible SN CP (snCP) and UP (snUP).
- We define processes for maintaining seamless connectivity with the overlay 6G NW, referred to as virtual connections. In particular, we propose Downlink (DL) and Uplink (UL) data flows via the MgtN, while also considering the procedures required for joining or exiting the SN.
- We define the *SN Tunnelling Protocol* (SN-TP) and the *SN Routing Protocol* (SN-RP) that enable the new architecture with the varying device types.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. In Section II, the new device types and roles are defined and the NW functionality is distributed within the SN. In Section III, the workflows for guaranteeing seamless connection with the overlay 6G NW considering mobility aspects are defined. Note that throughout the paper the existence of processes for selecting, joining and authenticating with the SN is assumed. The formation of a secure SN is also assumed. These processes are thus out of the scope of this paper.

II. DISTRIBUTION OF NETWORK FUNCTIONALITIES

Two classes of devices are considered, the *High Capability* (HC) and *Low Capability* (LC) devices as depicted in Fig. 1. The LC devices are constrained in their communication, computation, and/or power capabilities, or are incapable of even establishing a direct connection with the overlay NW on their own. The HC devices have higher computational and communication capabilities and can connect simultaneously to both the SN and the overlay NW. Note that this distinction could be either driven by physical constraints of a device or rather dynamic for a more capable device. This means that a specific device could potentially switch from LC to HC mode or vice versa (e.g., depending on their access to adequate power resources or their QoS requirements). The switching between LC to HC mode can be implemented by a UE taking

different factors (e.g., battery level, computation capability, thermal level, mobility state, etc.) into consideration.

Our goal is to have the SN management functionality towards the SN side to enable the aforementioned UCs within a more independent SN. For this reason, a new UE role is defined, in particular that of the MgtN [10]. This node is responsible for the local SN control and data routing, thus guaranteeing SN operation in the absence of an overlay NW (e.g. a BS). The MgtN acts as a gateway connecting SN nodes and the overlay 6G NW with the 6G NW offloading some of its routing and control functionalities to the MgtN. Naturally, this role can be exclusively taken by HC devices, due to the additional communication and computational resources required for managing the SN. MgtN devices must also have direct access to the 6G NW, to act as a gateway for the devices within the SN. Furthermore, it should be pointed out that this role is also a dynamic one, since a device might switch between LC and HC mode and hence withdraw from its role as MgtN or become one as a result.

Fig. 1: Exemplified SN topology.

Fig. 1 portrays an exemplified SN topology, where an HC UE is acting as a MgtN, managing the SN enclosed in the dashed square. Connected to this MgtN are three LC devices and another HC device. In this specific scenario, local SN control for local Intra-SN links is undertaken by the MgtN. Furthermore, the devices have been registered and managed by the overlay NW and they maintain a logical connection to the 6G-BS, while in the SN. Additionally, the SN HC devices can connect to the 6G-BS both directly using a single hop and indirectly using two hops via the MgtN, in a similar fashion to dual connectivity (DC) in NR [5]. In the following subsections, we delve into the specifics of the SN's CP and UP. The existing 3GPP framework does not provide such flexibility of changing roles among UEs in a SN while having the SN internal management being transparent to the Overlay NW, e.g., the BS.

A. Subnetwork Control Plane

There are two aspects to consider while designing the control plane in an SN: specialization and complexity. Regarding specialization, control, Radio Resource Management (RRM), and mobility procedures for example, might be different

Fig. 2: CP deployment terminating at the UE.

among different SNs depending on their purpose and also in comparison to the overlay 6G network. Hence, all control plane procedures need to be revisited, to ensure an efficient operation of all kinds of SNs. However, this study is beyond the scope of this paper, instead a separation of SN and overlay NW in terms of control is proposed. As depicted in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, the CP related to the overlay network remains terminated at the UE, while the transport of the related CP messages happens via the MgtN and the SN. The SN-specific control is handled by a separate entity, referred to as SN Control Plane (snCP), which is completely independent from the overlay NW. The snCP may be a simplified version of the CP handling the overlay NW, supporting only SN-related CP functions.

Fig. 3: CP deployment terminating at the MgtN.

As for the complexity, one can envision that some SN UEs may have limited HW capabilities and cannot process the full-fledged 6G CP messages. As depicted in Fig. 1 as well as in Fig. 3, UE2 offloads its CP functionality for communication with the overlay NW, or parts of it, towards the MgtN. This is done in order to save power or to reduce complexity of its own operation. The MgtN aggregates the CP of all the UEs served by the SN and translates it to an snCP entity. The snCP could also include offloaded UE CP information. The proposed architecture offers something that is not possible with SL (i.e., SL mode 1, SL mode 2 and SL relay). It allows for more autonomy in SN control with fewer dependencies to the overlay NW. This enables a more flexible SN architecture that is adaptable according to the use-case, whether in- or out-of-coverage. The same can be stated for IAB, where IAB donor nodes are tightly controlled by the NW and hence will not support such anticipated dynamic UC-driven formation of SNs.

B. Subnetwork User Plane

When an SN is formed, the nature of the UP within the SN could be very different from full-fledged 6G UP.

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 portray examples of an snUP used within the SN, where the 6G Layer2 (L2) protocols, i.e. *Medium Access Control (MAC)*, *Radio Link Control (RLC)* and *Packet Delivery Control Protocol (PDCP)* layers, terminate on the MgtN, and hence SN devices could be very much reduced in complexity, e.g.:

- No 3GPP PDCP specific ciphering and integrity capabilities are required anymore, resulting in reduced HW (see 5G NR PDCP [5]).
- No 3GPP compliant RLC handling with windowing, retransmissions, or reassembly buffers need to be implemented on the UE, requiring less memory on device (see 5G NR RLC [5]).
- No 3GPP compliant MAC layer is required on device, resulting in lower computational requirements (see 5G NR MAC [11]).

In summary, the proposed architecture allows flexible deployment of 3GPP layers within the SN, e.g. terminating at the MgtN, while having an snUP for the SN internal communication that is independent from the overlay NW. This offers new opportunities to optimize SNs for certain use-cases that cannot be achieved with the current 3GPP standard technologies (e.g., SL and IAB), allowing for new categories of devices that are able to connect to the 6G NW without having to support all mandatory capabilities.

III. SUBNETWORK WORKFLOWS FOR NETWORK CONTINUUM

After introducing an overview of the proposed SN architecture and how the snCP and snUP could look like, we are delving more into the required workflows for NW and SN interworking. In particular, we describe how SN nodes maintain a virtual connection with the overlay 6G NW as presented in Section III.A. In this context, the DL and UL end-to-end flows from the 6G NW to the SN nodes are also presented. In Section III.B, the processes for maintaining the virtual links when a node joins or leaves the SN are defined. In Section III.C, the handling of the UL grants at an SN level is investigated. Finally, in Sections III.D and III.E two flexible adaptation protocols are presented.

A. Virtual UE connections with 6G Network

On the NW side, the UE context and the related procedural efforts for the different devices within the SN can be significantly reduced. All link-related information (e.g., Physical layer configurations, measurement configurations, etc.) can be derived from the MgtN context. Fig. 4(a), gives a visual portrayal of this by showing how the 6G-BS maintains a new UE ID, called the SN_UEID. This SN_UEID is valid in RAN and it is assigned with the aid of the SN, while the UE is connected to the NW via the SN. Contexts of the specific UEs within the SN are linked to MgtN context via the SN_UEID at the 6G BS side.

This SN_UEID shall be mapped to the global NW UE ID of the particular UE in a 1-to-1 fashion, similar to the Temporary Mobile Subscriber Identity (TMSI) in 5G NR [12] (see Fig. 4),

(a) Virtual UE connection context at the BS.

(b) Message sequence chart for UL and DL flows.

Fig. 4: Virtual UE connections with 6G Network: (a) Deployment, (b) UL and DL flow.

in order to allow for seamless mobility in and out of the SN as explained in Section III.B. The SN_UEID is used by the BS for identifying and addressing the UEs within the SN, as well as also for data routing within the SN. An example flow of RRC message transmission initiated by UE1 is shown in Fig. 4 (b). In this example, UE1 is associated with an SN_UEID and this knowledge is shared among UE1, the MgtN and the BS. In the UL path, UE1 tags its data with its SN_UEID and sends it to MgtN using the local SN data transmission. By using the SN_UEID for routing, we achieve a degree of independence from lower-level transmission schemes (e.g. WiFi, SL, Ultrawideband or similar) that could be used within the SN. The MgtN forwards the received packet(s) with SN_UEID towards the BS. When the BS receives the packet(s) tagged with SN_UEID, it associates that packet with UE1's context. In the DL path, the BS creates a data packet and tags it with the SN_UEID of UE1 and then sends it to the MgtN. The latter reads the tag and forwards the packet to UE1 using the local SN-specific data transmission scheme.

B. Subnetwork Mobility

Another important aspect of the aforementioned virtual connections is the mobility of the SN devices. The process

of joining a SN and establishing the virtual link is portrayed in Fig. 5. It shows that UE4 is initially not part of the SN and connected with the BS. At some point, UE4 decides to join the SN managed by the MgtN (see Fig. 5 (a)). At first UE4, as shown in the MSC in Fig. 5 (b), requests a connection establishment via the MgtN. Subsequently, the BS associates UE4 with the MgtN that sent the request and assigns an SN_UEID. More specifically, the BS links UE4's context, SN_UEID, security context and other necessary information to the respective MgtN's context, essentially creating the logical link between BS and UE4 via this particular MgtN.

(a) Setup and logical configuration.

(b) Message sequence chart of the end-to-end configuration.

Fig. 5: UE4 joining an SN and establishing the virtual link.

For the case where a UE leaves the SN, the respective MSC is portrayed in Fig. 6. UE4 has already been associated with an SN_UEID by the BS, when it joined the SN. When the UE4 decides to leave the SN and connect to the BS directly, it performs a Random Access (RA) procedure. In order to allow seamless switching of the existing connection via the SN, UE4 shall send an RA Preamble (i.e., Message1) and start monitoring for a Message2 from the BS similarly to e.g., NR RA [13]. In Message3 the UE4 shall add its SN_UEID, so that the BS can identify that UE4 is the one that already has a context via the SN. This way, the BS can create a standalone context for UE4 and release the respective SN_UEID. Finally, the RA procedure continues, and the BS may apply necessary changes via e.g., RRC (re-)configuration or reestablishment in order to complete the connection setup.

C. Subnetwork Uplink flow

To limit the complexity of the MgtN and to not compromise the NW's ability to schedule UEs whether being inside or outside a SN, the following scheme is proposed to enable the

Fig. 6: Message sequence chart of UE4 leaving an SN to connect directly to the BS.

BS to schedule each UE individually. With the use of SNs, the BS should be provided with per-UE Buffer Status Report (BSR), for the UEs handled by the MgtN. This is essential to make the BS's scheduler aware of the individual needs of those UEs. Hence, the BS can provide UE-dedicated UL Grants towards the MgtN and ensure that the overall resource allocation among all UEs served by this BS (directly connected or via the SN) is done in a fair manner and is still under the NW's control.

When the MgtN receives per-UE grants, it shall honor them and schedule the UEs in the SN accordingly. One method to do that is the so-called "MgtN-buffered" approach, where the per-UE data is sent by the UEs and buffered at the MgtN. Hence, once the UL grant is received by the MgtN, UL transmission towards the BS can be performed right away by the MgtN. This implies higher memory requirements at the MgtN as well as higher overall latency, due to additional buffering. Note that the latter can be mitigated by mechanisms like preemptive BSR introduced for IAB [11]. Another option is the "on-demand scheduling", where the data remains buffered at the UE side and the UE-originated per-UE BSR is forwarded via the MgtN. In this case, the MgtN upon per-UE grant reception needs to perform an additional step of fetching the data from the UEs as required. Depending on the SN characteristics (e.g., the used radio technology, channel conditions, number of active UEs or resource availability), new scheduling restrictions may need to be imposed on the BS scheduler, to allow predictable scheduling through the SN.

To accommodate for SN link budget, the peak throughput per-UE could be set not to exceed a maximum transport block size. MgtN complexity could be limited by introducing a maximum capability for how many UEs can be scheduled in the same slot, or by applying individual TDD patterns per UE. A more flexible/dynamic per-UE PUSCH preparation time should be defined that allow for changes in latency requirements, depending on whether the UE is directly connected to the BS or it operates from within an SN. In the special case of the on-demand-scheduling, the PUSCH preparation time requirement could be different for initial HARQ transmission versus HARQ retransmissions, since the data is already avail-

Fig. 7: Subnetwork Tunneling Protocol (SN-TP).

able at the MgtN. Given the dynamic and flexible nature of the SN formed among UEs, the aforementioned capabilities need to be provided in a periodic or event driven manner upon change of the SN topology and available resources.

D. Subnetwork Tunneling Protocol

Following the 5G architecture, the UEs in an SN may have different QoS flows. In the context of SNs, this may result in multiple DRB entities established not only between the UE and the MgtN, but also between the MgtN and the 6G BS. In an extreme case, each QoS flow of a UE could be mapped to a MgtN-BS DRB in a 1-to-1 manner. For the sake of limiting the MgtN complexity in terms of the number of MgtN-BS DRB entities that should be maintained for the UEs within the SN, the SN-TP is proposed. The SN-TP is capable of aggregating data of different UEs or of different QoS flows of the same UE into fewer (even one) DRB entities between the MgtN and the BS.

The SN-TP Tx entity adds a header to each packet, mapping it to the specific UE and QoS flow it belongs to. In order to perform this mapping, the SN-TP Tx entity requires information provided by the SN. The added header is useful for the SN-TP Rx entity (i.e., 6G BS in UL and the MgtN in DL) in order to map / forward the packet to the respective radio bearer and UE. Explicitly, the SN-TP could be deployed on different layers depending on how the UE flows should be aggregated in the SN. Fig. 7 shows the deployment of SN-TP once above RLC in Example 1 and below RLC in Example 2. With the depicted deployment in Example 1, all UEs' DRBs could be multiplexed at the RLC layer into a single MgtN-BS RLC channel. Alternatively, similar QoS Flows of different UEs could be mapped to the same QoS Flow-related RLC channels or a single RLC channel per UE could be established. In Example 2 deployment, the aggregation will happen on MAC level enabling e.g. having RLC connections end-to-end.

Fig. 8: Subnetwork Routing Protocol (SN-RP).

The placement of the SN-TP in the RAN protocol stack could be a MgtN/NW capability and be agreed upon SN formation and/or reconfigured during the lifetime of the SN. Depending on the layer where SN-TP is deployed, different mapping information should be carried within the SN-TP header. More specifically, for the example of Fig. 7, the SN-TP header information would be SN_UEID, UE-MgtN RB ID.

E. Subnetwork Routing Protocol

In order to accommodate the flexibility of the snUP of Section II.B, a separate SN-RP is proposed to be used between devices within the SN. This protocol enables an adaptable deployment of different RAN protocol layers on different devices within the SN, without aligning this deployment with the overlay network.

The SN-RP shall be deployed above MAC and can accommodate the different L2 deployments (i.e., SDAP, PDCP, RLC) across the SN by carrying the necessary mapping information for the different layers between the different devices. Each UE that supports SN functionality shall be able to support the SN-RP. In addition, a new UE capability should be defined, indicating what layers a UE supports to be deployed on the device. For example, a UE may only support SDAP and PDCP on device and therefore relies on RLC being terminated on another node. The SN-RP delivers routing through the SN by including routing-related information per packet. It also carries mapping information in-band per packet, which is needed to perform the operations of the next protocol layer that is deployed at another node. The SN-RP flexibility is portrayed in Fig. 8. In that figure, there is a two-hop link between UE1 and the MgtN. Focusing on the UL direction, UE1 would send IP packets to UE2 by using the SN-RP layer and any local link technology for the transmission (e.g., Bluetooth). UE2 would then apply the SDAP and PDCP procedures to that packet and forward it to UE3, which is the MgtN, via any local link technology (e.g., WiFi). The MgtN would apply the RLC and MAC procedures and send it to the BS (e.g., via the cellular Uu interface).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have proposed a more flexible architecture that is adaptable to the anticipated UCs, due to increased

autonomy in SN control and having fewer dependencies to the overlay NW. We have considered new UE classes, namely the HC and LC devices, which are rather dynamic, as well as the role of the MgtN of an SN. Such flexibility of changing roles among UEs is not present in the current 3GPP framework. Furthermore, we distributed the NW functionalities and proposed flexible SN CP and UP, moving control closer to the UE. This allows for flexible deployment of 3GPP layers within the SN, e.g., terminating at the MgtN, while having an snUP for the SN internal communication that is independent from the overlay NW. We delved into the interaction of the SN with the overlay 6G NW. We investigated how to maintain UE connectivity within the SN with the concept of virtual connections. We also defined the main procedures to receive and transmit data within the SN from the 6G BS, while considering UE mobility. Finally, we proposed two decoupled adaptation protocols i.e., the SN-TP and the SN-RP for the MgtN-BS link and intra-SN communication, respectively. In a nutshell, the SN architecture has been presented boasting distributed NW functionality and seamless integration of SNs into the overlay 6G NW, something not possible with the existing 3GPP solutions. As next steps, the processes of selecting, joining and authenticating with the SN should be investigated to complete the SN architecture.

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